

HOW TO 'SO WHAT...?'
THE "DEATH AND TAXES" QUOTE(S):
PARTS I-IV

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SO WHAT...? PHILOSOPHY

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"You lye, you are not sure [...] 'tis impossible to be sure of anything but Death and Taxes--- therefore hold your Tongue [...]."

- Christopher Bullock, 1716

The Cobler of Preston, A Farce. As It is Acted at the Theatre-Royal in Lincoln's-Inn-Fields, London, 1716 (Fifth Edition: S. Bladon, London, 1767), p, 21.

"A Man can hardly refrain, after all that has been said, from flattering the Nation with Hopes, that they shall once more live to see themselves delivered from Task-masters, and Tax-gatherers. [...] This would be the reviving the Halcion Days, and bringing the Golden Age once more upon the Earth. Then it would be no more a Proverb or by-Word among us, that there is nothing sure, but Death and Taxes."

- Daniel De Foe, 1717

Fair Payment No Spunge: or, some considerations on the unreasonableness of refusing to receive back money lent on publick securities. And the necessity of setting the nation free from the insupportable burthen of debt and taxes. London: J. Brotherton, W. Meddows, J. Roberts, 1717, p. 75.

"But now, alas! this part is out of the question, not the man in the moon, not the groaning-board, not the speaking of friar Bacon's brazen-head, not the inspiration of mother Shipton, or the miracles of Dr. Faustus, things as certain as death and taxes, can be more firmly believed: the Devil not have a cloven foot!"

- Daniel De Foe, 1726

The Political History of the Devil. As Well Ancient as Modern: In Two Parts (T. Warner, London, 1726). From: *The Novels and Miscellaneous Works of Daniel De Foe, Vol. X.* Oxford: D. A. Talboys, 1840, p. 246.

"Our new Constitution is now established, and has an appearance that promises permanency; but in this world nothing can be said to be certain, except death and taxes."

- Benjamin Franklin, 1789

"Letter to M. Le Roy, 13 November, 1789" in: *The Works of Benjamin Franklin, Vol. XII*, (ed.) John Bigelow (Putnam's Sons, New York and London, 1904), p. 161.

INTRODUCTION

SO WHAT is it about these quotes that makes us smirk and squirm, chuckle and sigh, dislike yet agree? Is it a clever turn of practical 'wisdom'? A dark and sullen cynic's truth? An uneasy but resigned "such is life" realist's shrug?

I can tell you that the seeming wit of this coupling, 'death and taxes', the pretense of its wisdom and insight, the false façade and fake *factum* of this wanna-be *factum brutum*, are the hallmarks of both its danger and its ignorance. As we shall see from its occurrence in these different sources, the phrase is mostly *incidental*, such that it sneaks its way into various contexts merely as an offhanded witticism but never itself takes center stage. Such inadvertence and misdirection are actually essential to how it functions; it is treacherous precisely because it seems so innocuous.

Here we will consider the earliest written sources of this quotation. A quick look shows that the well-known, widely read and popular figure of Benjamin Franklin, who used the expression in a 1789 letter to Jean-Baptiste Le Roy, may be the likeliest and most widespread written occurrence that can account for its having become the familiar and popular sentiment that we know today. However, Franklin himself probably came across the formulation in the work of Daniel Defoe, who made use of it both in 1717 and again in 1726. Defoe, in turn, is likely to have seen or heard it in what appears to be its first written coinage in a play from 1716 by Christopher Bullock, *The Cobler of Preston*.

Without going into a full-fledged literary analysis of these sources, we can at least get a better sense of their historical contexts and the spirit of the phrase itself. I emphasize 'written' here because I would speculate that the expression was already a common idiom familiar to all of these authors, and was most likely commonly heard by word of mouth in social circles, at cafes, pubs, inns, etc. (but based on written evidence alone it is possible that Bullock really did coin the phrase for the first time). Either way, what we will see in these sources is both its incidental, seemingly harmless usage, as well as its deeper and otherwise unnoticed, more tragic significance.

PART I

First Source: Christopher Bullock, *The Cobler of Preston, A Farce, 1716.*

SO WHAT do we know about Christopher Bullock's *The Cobler of Preston*? One thing is that the work was already surrounded with a bit of controversy in its own time. Some have asserted that he may have stolen the play, or least the title and idea of it, from his contemporary playwright Charles Johnson. In fact one version of events tells of a pickpocket who was hired to steal a description of Johnson's lead character. It is a compelling sleuth tale but it seems unlikely (drama and theater surround the theatrical dramatists, indeed). It is true, however, that Johnson also wrote a play bearing the very same title at roughly the same time as Bullock, and that the two knew about each other's having done so. Yet while Johnson's work is a musical farce focused on the politics of the Jacobite revolution at the time, Bullock's play, also farcical (as the title indicates), focuses more on class struggle, sexism and gender roles. For a more detailed and researched account of Bullock's and Johnson's versions and background, I recommend the article by Charles Conaway. "Shakespeare, Molly House Culture, and the Eighteenth-Century Stage" (Comparative Drama, Vol. 38, No. 4, Winter 2004-05, pp. 401-423).

As Conaway explains both Bullock and Johnson were influenced directly by Shakespeare's *The Taming of the Shrew*. Bullock made this influence explicit as part of an open acknowledgment in his Preface that the play stems directly from Shakespeare's "Induction" (the larger initial setting in which the main play-within-a-play takes place). For our purposes it is Bullock's work where we find the first instance of the death and taxes quote when his main character, Toby Guzzle, claims "... 'tis impossible to be sure of anything but Death and Taxes." Here we may consider how it is both Incidental and more Significant.

Incidental

The scene in which Guzzle utters this phrase is already humorous. Like the character Sly in Shakespeare's "Induction," Toby Guzzle wakes from a drunken sleep and is tricked into thinking he is a Lord and Judge, and that his previous life, including his work as a Cobbler, his wife Dorcas, and the inn-keeper Hacket to whom he owes money, are all just a dream he's been having for the past fifteen years. The character who orchestrates this trick is an actual Lord named Jasper, along with his servants, who have convinced Guzzle that none of his previous life was real. Just as Guzzle is coming to believe the farce, he is made to sit as Judge for a case. The case turns out to be that between Hacket the inn-keeper and his actual wife Dorcas. Hacket accuses Dorcas of slandering her, which she did when they were arguing about the money that Guzzle owes to Hacket for all of the drinking, eating, and breaking of glasses he's done at her Inn. Now believing that he is a Judge, Guzzle hears the case. This is part of their exchange:

Guzzle: What was your husband's name?

Dorcas: Guzzle, Toby Guzzle, so please you.

Guzzle: Pha! Pha! You know not what you say, Woman; 'tis all a dream, I tell you.

Dorcas: Indeed my Lord, 'tis true.

Guzzle: How! Sure I know better than you, you Baggage: would you give the lye to Authority? Throw the Lye into the very face of Authority?--I tell you I am Authority, and were I to say the Moon is made of Mustard-Pot, you must believe it [...] I say 'tis all a Dream, you have no Husband, nor is there any such a man as Toby Guzzle.

Dorcas: I know what your Honour means, but I'm sure----

Guzzle: You lye, you are not sure; for I say, Woman, 'tis impossible to be sure of anything but Death and Taxes---therefore hold your Tongue, or you shall both be soundly whipped--Sure I know my office [...] Why I was in a Dream for fifteen Years myself, and dreamt I marry'd you--Dorcas is your name?

Dorcas: Toby! Odds-daggers! Mr Justice's Honour, my Husband! A Lord, with a pox to you! I'll claw you, you Dog!

Guzzle: Lay hold on her-----

Hacket: Ah, you Carrion Cur, do we come to you for Justice?

Guzzle: She's in a Dream too, lay hold on her----- (p. 21)

The phrase about death and taxes here is incidental to the actual substance of the scene and plot of the play. Its use is rhetorical in order to strengthen Guzzle's claim that Dorcas can't be sure or certain of anything, etc. Yet indirectly, there is a much deeper significance to the phrase that can only be grasped when we consider the other points that Guzzle makes about Authority. The sinister significance of what this phrase actually represents is thus hidden in plain sight, so to speak, and works by means of misdirection and inadvertence.

Significant

The deeper meaning of this phrase can be more clearly seen when we consider Shakespeare's play from which Bullock's is derived. In Shakespeare's work, and by extension Bullock's as well, there is a more primordial conflict at stake, a kind of dichotomy between 'nature' and 'nurture', wild and tamed, primitive and civilized, etc. The apparent conflict takes shape first with the character Sly, an impoverished drunkard, who, in the "Induction," is tricked into believing that he is a wealthy Lord with a wife (a male Page is told by his Lord to dress up and pretend to be her). Thus Bullock's play is an extension of this "Induction." As part of the ruse in Shakespeare's version, Sly and his false wife are shown a play for entertainment, i.e., the main part of *The Taming of the Shrew* featuring the characters Petruchio and Katharina, wherein the former 'tames' the latter and marries her.

It is the manner in which Katharina is 'tamed' that requires more serious consideration, and it is the transformation of her character that leads us to the deeper significance at work. Bullock, however, also hits upon this theme when Guzzle claims that what the Authority says is true, and that it is true because the Authority says so. This is the sinister trend that also (seemingly) characterizes Katharina's complete transformation by the end of Shakespeare's play. What happened to her? She not only proclaims her

obedience to Petruccio, now her husband, but even chastises the other wives for not being obedient and subservient enough to their own!

Here one is reminded of works such as Orwell's *1984* and Huxley's *A Brave New World*, and many such dystopian tales that portray the power of coercion, propaganda, mind control and the darker side of 'nurture' in the 'nature/nurture' dichotomy. It may be that Burgess' *A Clockwork Orange* presents a counter-example to these instances of 'taming' and 'reform', but then again the utter depravity of the character Alex who seems to break this cycle and the system that tried to break him, is therefore no real testament to a hopeful outcome. Neither is there much hope in Kesey's *One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest* regarding Randal McMurphy's fate; although there is perhaps something further to consider in Chief Bromden's escape, and perhaps it is precisely a character such as Chief Bromden to whom we should be looking with respect to our overall theme in order to understand the deeper significance of 'death and taxes'.

Once the parallels between these characters are glimpsed, we can also then recognize the philosophical debates that are recurrent with Industrialization, the Enlightenment, Romanticism and other earlier phases of thought in terms of theories about a 'natural' human state in relation to the role and influence of education and culture. These debates and the underlying conflict that they reveal stretches further into the past in many diverse and famous works, such as Ibn Tufayl's *Hayy Ibn Yaqzan*, Plato's *Republic*, and indeed all the way back to the first 'recorded' story, *The Epic of Gilgamesh*.

Clearly such various works do not all say the same thing, far from it. They do, however, either take up similar themes in different contexts, are responses to their predecessors, or somehow arrive at a similar and deeper conflict from various perspectives and lines of inquiry. Thus, we begin to uncover what is entrenched and buried within our subject, this coupling of 'death and taxes'. There is a fundamental conflict which leads not only to incidentally comedic, but also to significantly tragic transformations.

As we continue next time with our questions about these quotations and their use of the dubious couplet, we will hopefully gain an even deeper insight into what's at stake for us today. For it may be that this ancient tension takes a new turn and has a new twist, in this, our still 'new' century... **Part II, coming soon!**

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Posted: April 8, 2026

PART II

The Defoe Quotes (From Utopia to the Devil's Foot)

SO WHAT about the name; is it Daniel 'De Foe' or 'Defoe'? Originally it was written 'De Foe' but it has become standard to write 'Defoe'. When citing the quotations up at the top, I decided to preserve the original 'De Foe', but throughout the prose I am using 'Defoe'. Same person; my odd decision to preserve them both.

The first Defoe quote contradicts what I have said so far about the phrase 'death and taxes' being used in an only 'incidental' way (see 'Part I'). In this quote, it is anything but incidental, indeed the whole pamphlet in which this quotation appears may be said to culminate in a criticism and aspiration to move beyond the idiom itself. In the second Defoe quotation, however, the phrase resumes its default incidental role. The fact that the same author uses the same idiom both as a focal point to overcome, on the one hand, and in the usual incidental manner, on the other, only goes to show that when it is not used incidentally, it becomes an object of derision, as indeed it should.

Our purpose here in Part II is not so much to give a detailed account of the two sources themselves, but rather to see how the phrase 'death and taxes' is used following our incidental/significant distinction, and likewise expand upon what has been said in Part I about the (always problematic) nature/nurture distinction. To simplify things for this section, we may see 'death' as nature, and 'taxes' as nurture (in the sense of a custom and social practice). To better understand the dubiousness of their coupling, we turn to Defoe.

Defoe's two quotes show us both the truth and the façade of the couplet 'death and taxes'.

Significant

In the first quote Defoe refers to the phrase directly, envisioning a time when the expression is not only not taken for a 'by-word' or a commonplace, but indeed would likely not even be understood at all due to its obvious absurdity.

For it is obviously absurd: death and taxes are not at all similar. We are absurd for seeing them as similar, indeed even 'understanding' their being placed together as a pair and finding humor in the pairing's cleverness! Yet this is how the phrase functions. For it is precisely because their comparison is obviously untrue and absurd (i.e., that the necessary cycle of growth and decay which underlies all natural living phenomena could be anything like the completely unnecessary, made up bureaucratic practice of taxation), that we find it humorous and clever, and start to think "oh but ha, there's some truth in it!" Thus do we make it so, and then accept it as somehow inevitable, a necessity.

We have tamed ourselves. We have tamed our own shrewdness into the subservient acceptance of an obvious absurdity; just as Winston is tortured by Big Brother into saying $2+2=5$, so too have we tamed ourselves into saying that $\text{death+taxes}=\text{necessary}$. At least Winston had to be tortured, for apparently all we really need to do is feign some cleverness; being desperate to gain approval and even the false appearance of wisdom, we have turned an obvious absurdity into a 'witty', good-sensed practical person's truism.

Incidental

How absurd is it? Defoe's second quote heaps it upon us, compounding the self-convinced disposition of one absurdity upon the next, until it all sounds true. I will explain what I mean.

Set theory is perhaps a good example (or in many ways any computation with unimaginably large or small quantities). It is obvious that we cannot exactly understand infinity, but we are able to not understand it so well that we can speak of different 'kinds' of infinity, and can deal with those different infinite sets (none of which we fully comprehend) through otherwise fairly ordinary and comprehensible mathematical operations. In the Defoe quote, he is 'simply' illustrating how convinced people are that the Devil has a cloven hoof for a foot by imitating the indignation of one whose belief in that 'fact' might be challenged. Such a person would sooner deny the much more widely accepted 'truths' (a series of absurdities) culminating in the ultimate absurdity, 'death and taxes', before questioning the cloven-footedness of the Devil.

Just to be clear, I am not making an argument against set theory or in any way calling it nonsensical. Quite the contrary, I use it here to illustrate how we are able to make sense of things that are not immediately apparent and can do it successfully. However, such an ability is also the manner in which we can be lulled or fooled into thinking that something which is blatantly absurd might have some logic to it, i.e., that taxes are as 'certain' as death.

Admittedly Defoe's second quote is a strange passage and difficult to follow especially from our present historical context and current conventions of speech and grammar. However, Defoe illustrates the absurdity of one conviction by having us imagine someone who supports that conviction through a series of other absurdities, thereby both giving the rhetorical illusion of a reasoned argument while at the same time sending us into an ever deepening swamp of untruth from which we simply cannot hope to resurface or recover.

Significant

The genius and beauty of Defoe's doing so is that we are at least made to laugh for the right reasons; he not only highlights the oddity of the things we take to be true, but at the same time shows how we use those oddities as certainties in order to demonstrate the certainty of yet other more far-fetched oddities. If it were an axiomatic system, one would be using the falsehood of one proposition in order to demonstrate the truth of the next falsehood (or some such).

The absurd coupling of 'death and taxes', then, takes its place among these false propositions, and indeed claims its rank as being the proudest and chief-most 'certainty' among them all (excepting that of the Devil's cloven feet, of course).

In **Part III** (coming soon!) we will bring this 'So What...?' discussion into our more immediate everyday attitudes and experiences by reference to one of those American 'founding fathers', Benjamin Franklin, whose popularity has seemingly helped 'seal the deal' and tightened the certainty around our false convictions. It's time to break the seal....

Posted: April 16, 2026

PART III

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Two Revolutions, One Delusion: Franklin's Letter to LeRoy (Humble Hubris, Hubristic Humility)

SO WHAT new thing could we possibly say about Benjamin Franklin; Franklin who is so well-known, shines so bright in the spotlight, that he is difficult to see? A 'founding father' of the United States of America, an inventor, scientist, entrepreneur, statesman, etc.... The biographies and books abound, there are documentaries, films, even a recent Netflix series. The only insights about him that I can add will be with regard to our focus on his Letter to Jean-Baptiste Le Roy in which Franklin uses the phrase "death and taxes," and to whom the phrase itself is often credited without reference to its earlier instances.

What is most striking about Franklin's Letter is the immediate juxtaposition between his seemingly significant use of the term 'Philosophy', and the contrasting incidental use of the 'death and taxes' idiom. It is precisely a lack of philosophical awareness in utilizing the idiom (displayed by the otherwise quite cognizant Franklin) that typifies the insidious and unnoticed manner in which the idiom operates. It works because we do not know it is working.

The actual significance of the phrase functions through its incidental use. It is jovial, sharp-witted but light, seemingly harmless; it conveys an attitude that camouflages its detrimental effect, thereby allowing such detriment to flourish undetected - hiding in plain sight - for all and no one to see.

Yet Franklin's brief Letter to his friend and colleague, the French physicist John-Baptiste LeRoy, also upholds a commonplace and unimpressive dichotomy between 'those who are thoughtful', on the one hand, and 'the mob' or masses of those who are not, on the other. Franklin's sentiment is one that we are so accustomed to hearing (and possibly believing) that we barely notice it: that of the 'thoughtful few' vs. the 'mindless many', the educated vs. the uneducated, the upper vs. lower, the better vs. the worse. It is so commonplace, in fact, that many highly educated people are themselves rather uneducated about their own espousal of it, just as far too many otherwise clever people (whether highly educated or not) likewise too often employ their (now hopefully recognized as un-clever) coupling, "death and taxes."

In Franklin's case, we find that while he distinguishes between the violent ignorance of a mob compared to the philosophical understanding of reflective individuals, he is nevertheless himself guilty of missing the unreflective nature of his own 'witticism'. To get a better sense of the distinction that Franklin utilizes, it is helpful a look at the Letter itself. Note how the 'mob' is presented with a kind of choice: people can either see LeRoy as a 'monopolizer of knowledge', or as a 'monopolizer of corn'. Franklin writes:

It is now more than a year since I have heard from my dear friend Le Roy. What can be the reason? Are you still living? Or have the mob of Paris mistaken the head of a monopolizer of knowledge for a monopolizer of corn, and paraded it about the streets upon a pole. (160)

This strikes us as a rather dark but amusing way of asking a friend if he is still alive, and indeed of introducing the theme of death in a witty fashion. We get a glimpse of Franklin's style here, for he seems sincerely concerned about his friend's welfare, is disarming in his humor, but also wants some 'intel' on what is happening in France. It is difficult not to be drawn in by Franklin's friendly yet skillful devices. Nevertheless, the dichotomy is about to take shape, and our attention is mainly drawn to the following lines, where Franklin himself emphasizes the word 'Philosophy':

Great part of the news we have had from Paris, for near a year past, has been very afflicting. I sincerely wish and pray it may all end well and happy, both for the king and the nation. The voice of Philosophy I apprehend can hardly be heard among those tumults. [Franklin's italics] (160)

Not only does he emphasize Philosophy, but indeed even personifies and gives it a 'voice' that can be heard - can be, that is, but probably is not. Ironically, it is Franklin himself who nevertheless does not seem to hear the philosophical voice when he employs the 'death and taxes' idiom below. Franklin presents yet another variation on the incidental and the significant use of this coupling. In a way, he actually synthesizes them:

Our new Constitution is now established, and has an appearance that promises permanency; but in this world nothing can be said to be certain, except death and taxes. (161)

Whether he realizes it or not, Franklin's words here are brimming with incidental significance. On the one hand he speaks of the new U.S. Constitution (note how the word 'constitution', as we would in a political philosophy class, bears an almost organic sense, the 'life' of a government and society, its laws - that of which it consists, even perhaps its 'being'). Of course this sort of meaning predates the U.S. and other modern Constitutions by millennia, but its use in terms of coming into being, a promise of 'permanency', the fragile ground in which it has been planted... all of this reminds us of the first of the two terms i.e., 'death', in the phrase 'death and taxes'.

I do not think Franklin himself is completely aware of this connection as he writes it, but that is the incidental aspect of how easily this language of life and death itself permeates the metaphorical, or at least initially metaphorical, way in which we think of things. In fact, before bidding his friend 'adieu', Franklin speaks of his own constitution and death:

My health continues much as it has been for some time, except that I grow thinner and weaker, so that I cannot expect to hold out much longer. (161)

Thus, Franklin's Letter really does epitomize the final interweaving and stronghold of how the coupling 'death and taxes' is as we've described it - insidious, operating in plain sight for everyone and no one to see. In one fell swoop Franklin both is philosophical and is not when he laments the likely lack of philosophical reflection on the part of the 'mob', yet fails to recognize his own lack of philosophical

reflection by deploying the death and taxes idiom. He both does call our attention to the distinction and impossible comparison between human governance via taxation and the natural process of death, and does not when he brings the very impermanence/permanence of the U.S. Constitution into focus and then speaks of his own inevitable impermanence. He gives into a notion of 'legacy', a model of remembrance: the ironically hubristic humility that our human creations will perhaps overcome our natural limitations.

The Constitution shows the "promise" of permanence, says Franklin, while he himself fades away. In other words, while Franklin himself will die, the Constitution, and the taxation along with it that he helped to establish, has taken hold and even promises to become a lasting certainty. Such is the operation of our humble hubris, our hubristic humility without our being aware of it, and such is what this phrase 'death and taxes' reveals. Our delusion that, despite ourselves, we can somehow match, perhaps even outmatch, death. Yet we indulge this delusion not by claiming it explicitly, but by slyly believing that our own devices, in this case taxes, can accomplish the same level of inevitability as that of death.

We shall attempt to discern how even the term 'taxes' must ultimately succumb to its own (more subversively natural) origins - its root meaning, its origin myth - both in lieu of and despite the manner in which it is used in the phrase 'death and taxes' today. We will provide a retelling of this myth in **Part IV (The 'Conclusion')**, coming soon!

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PART IV The Hero and The Villain

SO WHAT have we learned thus far, what remains to be said, and what further questions should we ask regarding this dubious coupling, 'death and taxes'?

Nature's ways are always guiding us whether we realize it or not, even when we want to differentiate 'nurture' and 'culture', they are themselves both fundamentally natural and biological notions. What does *not* fit in with all of this is *taxes* as an obligatory payment, a method of administrative control, or even as a punitive measure.

We can speak adjectivally of 'taxing' difficulties, of challenges and hardships, and if the idiom employed the term in this sense then there would be some semblance, perhaps, between death and taxes. Yet that is precisely *not* how it is meant. 'Taxes' in the 'death and taxes' coupling is explicitly meant to be as unnatural as possible, the 'inevitable' albeit unfortunate 'necessity' of payment, a kind of no-alternative outcome of our self-organization into communities and society. It is in this latter sense that the idiom functions and a coupling of taxes with death is made, i.e., as an attempt to obtain the impossible status of a natural process (note I avoid the term 'natural law' or 'law of nature' - an oxymoron *par excellence*, for laws are 'by nature' *not* 'natural', but that's another blog post).

Taxes are a human hubris that punishes itself. Death is not a punishment. We saw in **Part III** the **Humble Hubris, Hubristic Humility** of a phrase that tries to place taxes on the same level as death and mortality. In this sense taxes are a simulacra of death, an attempt to be as inevitable as death. In that attempt they are hubristic, and in their hubris not only do they fail, but they are also a self-imposing punishment for trying to be death's equal, trying to be inevitable. I say 'they' as though taxes were the agents of their hubris, but of course they are human hubris attempting to create an inevitability, to 'nurture' a custom that is as certain as death is a certainty of 'nature'.

Being confronted with this quagmire we've made for ourselves when we use, accept, and even (nervously) chuckle at this idiom, seeing but not seeing its oddly self-imposed and self-punishing hubris permeate its light- (but actually heavy-) hearted expression, I cannot help but imagine, by contrast, the laughter of Laozi (or Lao Tzu, Lao Tze, Lao Tse...) whose name, unlike the Way or Tao, *can* be said but apparently not so easily written (at least not in Roman letters). Laozi laughs because he takes joy in seeing how even in an attempt to differentiate ourselves from nature and then try to establish ourselves as its equal through imitation and dominance, even then, the Way of nature is at work. Every attempt to describe it, and even attempts to say how our descriptions are themselves natural, is an example of how it cannot actually be articulated in any way other than how it already articulates itself simply by being (and thus we end up writing sentences like the one I've just written).

Perhaps the problem lies in the words themselves, then? It is worth noting how the *Etymonline* site (which has its limitations but is still a good initial resource for basic etymologies, and still better, in my view, than the auto-generated Google search results) explains the term for both the verb 'tax' and the noun 'tax':

tax(v.)

c. 1300, taxen, "impose a tax on; demand, require, impose (a penalty)," from Old French taxer "impose a tax" (13c.) and directly from Latin taxare "evaluate, estimate, assess, handle," also "censure, charge," probably a frequentative form of tangere "to touch" (from PIE root *tag- "to touch, handle").

The meaning "subject (someone) to taxation" is from early 14c. The sense of "to burden, put a strain on" is recorded from early 14c.; the figurative use in this sense is by 1670s. The meaning "censure, reprove" is from 1560s. Its use in Luke ii in reference to the census translates Greek apographein "to enter on a list, enroll" is due to Tyndale. Related: Taxed; taxing.

tax(n.)

early 14c., "obligatory contribution levied by a sovereign or government," from Anglo-French tax, Old French taxe, and directly from Medieval Latin taxa, from Latin taxare (see tax (v.)). Related: Taxes.

Tax-gatherer is attested from 1550s. Tax-dodger "one who avoids payment of a tax or taxes" is by 1876. Tax-deduction is from 1942; tax-shelter is attested from 1961; tax-break by 1968; tax-bracket by 1975. (*Etymonline*)

What is missing from these listings is the Ancient Greek *taxis*. In biology we see this sense in the term 'taxonomy', and in Ancient Greek mathematics as *taxis* (e.g., Euclid's *Elements*, especially Book X), and the original title of Ptolemy's *Syntaxis* (or as we know it from the Arabic translation, *Almagest*). All of these uses (including music and military contexts with the Ancient Greek) have to do with an ordering and organization. And this brings us to a complex issue regarding the origins of writing in relation to oral traditions. It casts our gaze back to Cuneiform and Mesopotamia, to the Sumerian, Akkadian and Babylon languages. I mentioned *The Epic of Gilgamesh* in **Part I** of this series, and perhaps now is an opportunity to better understand why.

Thus, in place of more critical analysis, I'd like to tell at least the beginnings of a myth (*mythos*), or as Plato might say, a 'likely' story (*logos*). And since I have spent much of the time railing against the idiom in question, our story should probably include a Villain of some sort to better illustrate the significance of 'death and taxes' as a kind of dupe's 'stupor-truth', i.e., the seeming *certainty* of *both* death *and* taxes and why Laotzi would laugh at this (but he would do so for different reasons than those that make most people chuckle when they hear the expression).

To tell the beginnings of such a story then will probably require a certain figure, a Villain whose motives and logic will highlight the nature and operation of what can only be described as an insidious 'spirit' within our midst, and one that we would all do well to learn how to recognize both within ourselves and throughout our day-to-day lives. I'll even provide the moral in advance:

Where uninhibited tranquility is strength, power unchecked is weakness.

The Villain

Our Villain's name is *J. Bureau*. The following is an account of his origins, his motives, and his gradual rise to power. There are no extant primary sources of Bureau himself, so our inquiries and history must remain speculative and limited until further research is conducted and more direct evidence can be obtained.

From what we know, J. Bureau has gone by many different names, and his presence reaches far back into antiquity. This particular version of the name, 'J. Bureau', is only the most recent and modern manifestation. It is important to note also that our J. Bureau does not seem to be in any way related to the descendants of the 'Bureau' family, whose line is usually traced back to Normandy in the 14th century. Indeed there is also no specific given name for the abbreviation 'J.', either. (Although some have referred to him as 'Jacques', 'Jack', and even 'Joe', but none of these bear historical accuracy.) Still, I find that 'Jacques Bureau' has a nice ring to it. If anything, our subject has merely adopted this first initial and surname without specifying a full identifier, and may have done so ironically simply to enjoy using the initials 'J.B.'.

So What are the origins of this Villain? Before Gilgamesh was pursuing the fountain of youth in an attempt to overcome death and mortality, scribes in ancient Mesopotamia were already etching out cuneiform tablets, indeed marking out one of the earliest known *bureaucracies*. It is speculated that, somehow, within the discarded clay shavings nicked out by the stylus-wielding scribes, in the unwanted piles, there began to emerge a kind of smoldering, an effluence fueled by the first feelings of monotony that took hold of the otherwise magical work that went into producing these earliest writings. In that befouled and smoldering mound were the first noxious signs of this spirit, this monotonizing entity now known as 'J. Bureau'. This new toxin quickly spread into the breath and minds of the scribes, thus making them the first 'bureaucrats'.

However, the suggestion that Bureau's toxic presence resulted from these 'clay shavings' of the scribes is most likely untrue, for in fact a simple glance at any of the numerous ancient clay tablets will show that the process of writing was more a kind of angled indentation, producing small imprints into the soft clay in accordance with the pressure of the scribes' styluses. There may have been some excess clay notched out, but the tablets were made mostly by pushing the clay down rather than being 'carved' out as some might imagine. The clay itself was still soft when being inscribed and then later dried into the more solid (and thus breakable) tablets that are so ubiquitous in archaeological digs to this day.

Nevertheless, Bureau's being an unintended consequence of the scribal activity is quite real. While the material and physical dynamic of the clay's involvement is also real, the physical aspect of Bureau's origins resulted mostly from a different process. We must therefore consider the connection between otherwise distinct activities, i.e., the physical manifestation of the toxin via clay on the one hand, and the inadvertent social (and scribal) intoxication that it caused, on the other.

Two basic principles should be established at this point: 1) All human labor runs the risk of becoming mindless labor, or more precisely (as indicated above), *monotonous*. 2) All monotonous labor is vulnerable to bureaucratization; its purpose, dynamics, liveliness, sonority, polyphony and tonality are drawn upon, drawn (led) out, extracted (ex-ducere, 'educated') and siphoned into fueling the very structure that seeks to organize, exploit and 'tax' it. The energy of the work and labor itself becomes taxed in order to tax it. It is a relationship similar to that of host (work) and parasite (bureaucracy).

Monotony is a fascinating term. Clearly it is derived from a combination of 'monas'/'mono-', meaning 'one', and the term 'tone', such that 'mono-tone' means 'one-tone' or 'single tone'. It has gone from this literal sense of a single tone to the more everyday sense of something repetitive, 'boring' or tedious. Indeed, what is *bureaucracy itself* if not precisely that, i.e., repetitive, boring and tedious?

The long yawn of the bureaucrat's, scribe's or student's tedium is perhaps the very inhaling gasp by which J. Bureau's toxin entered the minds and bodies of ancient scribes, students and workers alike, whereas those in power, due to their weakness and lack of tolerance, would have been over-stimulated by the same ingredient (they are what teenagers in my day would have called 'lightweights').

One question these principles raise is: whether or not such monotony and exploitative taxation is necessary or inevitable. Are there any variables that preclude such an outcome?

In the case of cuneiform in Mesopotamia and Sumeria, there are at least four factors which seem especially relevant to the bureaucratization and taxation of labor: 1) education, 2) agriculture focused on crops and centralized storage of harvests, 3) mass production of materiel (pottery, tools, textiles...), and 4) architecture. It is interesting to compare these elements with what now appear to be older prehistoric societies, especially those in Ancient Amazonia that have only recently been discovered and are now slowly becoming better understood. In particular we note that these civilizations *did* have agriculture and architecture, but were not focused on centralized harvest storage or administration, and as far as we know they did not produce written texts. Instead there is a long tradition of cave art, geoglyphs and oral storytelling.

We must wonder, then: is the taxing spirit of Bureau and centralized administration more directly aligned with the development of writing, and with only certain types of administrative agriculture, than with the two factors just mentioned?

The Hero, The Villain, and the Scribes

Perhaps it is not writing itself that gives rise to the Villain J. Bureau, but rather the corruption of why writing was created in the first place. The story of Gilgamesh was, it is thought, first recorded around 2100 BC, and not standardized until 1600 BC. The poetry of the priestess Enheduana, however, predates even the first written account of Gilgamesh by two centuries, and she herself was writing in around 2300 BC. Enheduana then, was both author and scribe, and she is the Hero in this tale.

Let us continue exploring the origins of our characters. One thing we tend to overlook, especially today, is the manner in which things either thrive or perish, that both thriving and perishing happen in myriad ways. Files, machines, documents, hardware and even software can be destroyed without much incident. Memories shared, stories told, heard and retold with explanations and interpretations, although subject to variation, are not so easily deleted when humans themselves are the ones telling, hearing, retelling and recreating them. In all of this, Plato (as always) looms large. His story of Thoth (or Theuth), the remedy-poison-cure of writing, of the conflict between repetition vs. live speech, poetic encoding vs. logical decoding, live argument and dialogue vs. un-listening written and recorded speeches delivered as orations, but memorized or rehearsed by the orators (perhaps with written notes

before the performance), and the fact that Plato captures all of it simultaneously in a *written dialogue* in which he 'retells' or 'makes up' a myth about the invention of writing, it's all wonderfully dizzying.

Dizzying and intoxicating like the lines of Enheduana as she breathes, sings, writes and recites her prayers and praises to Inana (Ishtar), doing so into both air *and* clay. Of course, whether she herself wrote her own writings is a topic of debate among scholars. Although it is accepted that she was alive in 2500 BC, the surviving texts of her work were transcribed circa. 1750 BC.

Unfortunately this debate could be crucial to our retelling and our tale, and it creates a dilemma. I will try to articulate the question (truly writing a good question is one of the most difficult and meaningful tasks we can set for ourselves).

If Enheduana did not write her own words (if they were her own words, which is also under debate), but instead they were preserved orally and then eventually written down only later by scribes for purposes that were already infected by the noxious fumes and spirit of Bureau, the administrators and power grabbers, then does writing itself ever truly escape Bureau, either in early history or even now? If Laozi says the Way cannot be said, and therefore cannot be written either, then does writing that it cannot be said not put us into the very intoxicating stupor-illusion of hubris released by the Villain Bureau? In other words, is there a Hero who wrote without being corrupted by Bureau, or is the very notion of her having done so just part of the Villain's story? Is writing possible without corruption, or is that possibility itself only one of the illusions of its intoxication? *Is* Jacques Bureau inevitable? Are taxes?

Much seems at stake. We can look a little further into the debate regarding Enheduana's actual written authorship in order to figure out how our likely story/myth should be retold.

A couple of things are worth clarifying from the outset. First the cuneiform texts that people discuss fall into different categories because cuneiform was used for writing down different languages. The language of Enheduana was Sumerian. Aside from Sumerian the other significant language grouping of Mesopotamia is Akkadian, which is then divided into Babylonian and Assyrian. (So the *Epic of Gilgamesh*, for example, is in the Babylonian language). Thus there is one significant degree of separation to bear in mind, namely that while the script is cuneiform, the languages are different. The extent to which that distinction will be relevant to our question remains to be seen, but it is important to have in mind.

The most recent authoritative text on Enheduana which includes all of the writings attributed to her is *Enheduana: The Complete Poems of the World's First Author*, by Sophus Helle (2023). There Helle acknowledges the debate in question and states clearly that it is still a debate. However, he reminds us that either way, whether she wrote or even authored verbally the works, they are indeed about her, a true historical figure, and she is the first "author" to have been recognized as an "author" by her own tradition. Helle is right, also, to remind us that being such a significant historical person, the lack of popular notoriety and more common recognition of her very existence is inexcusable. Patriarchy is obviously to blame most of all, but there are also other factors which pervade our human priorities and never fail to disappoint when it comes to what we commonly know and what we don't, what is popular and what is not. Our priorities are a mess, in short, and in fact when you think about it that means that our priorities are not, in fact, our actual priorities - we just believe that they are.

It is possible to make some distinctions especially between Enheduana's hymn, the *Exultation of Inana*, and the figure and role of the same goddess Ishtar (the Akkadian version of the name) in the *Epic of Gilgamesh*. *Gilgamesh*, however, was also a story told in Sumerian, so it did not originate necessarily later, but it existed in various forms and parts before becoming the Babylonian epic that is read in most classrooms today. There are many other texts besides those of Enheduana and those about Gilgamesh in both Sumerian and Akkadian to consult, and it may well all be an oversimplification on my part, but the obvious shift between the portrayal and function of this goddess Inana/Ishtar in these two likewise very different texts (one a hymn, the other an epic) is too compelling to ignore.

Indeed, the differing portrayals of the goddess have not been ignored by leading scholars in the field. Helle (mentioned above) addresses these differences, along with Pryke, Harris, and many others. However, the particular interest we have here was hinted at in **Part I**, where we saw a thematic connection in the nature/nurture issue and different literary works including *One Flew Over the Cuckoo's Nest, 1984, A Brave New World, A Clockwork Orange, The Cobbler of Preston, The Taming of the Shrew* and *Gilgamesh*. We can add the portrayals of Inana/Ishtar to these threads that weave the theme together, and many other works both old and new besides.

To put it briefly, the Inana described by Enheduana is incredibly powerful, basically a force of nature - and as such is capable of representing polar opposites such as destruction and creation, being nurturing and wrathful, vengeful and protective, good, bad, and every kind of *coincidentia oppositorum* one can think of. The Ishtar of *Gilgamesh*, on the other hand, is jealous, petty, spiteful but still dangerous. Whole books have been written on these distinctions, so we cannot investigate all of the complexities here. Yet I am not sure that any scholar has drawn the deeper insight into Enheduana's portrayal. Even though Harris uses the most important phrase *coincidentia oppositorum*, the philosophical significance is not fully explored. For that, we would have to turn to thinkers like Alan Watts and Iain McGilchrist, who rightfully draw a philosophical thread from Laozi to Heraclitus and Nicolas von Cusa, among others. Watts also investigates various Chinese, Indian and other mythological traditions, including that of Christianity, in his book *The Two Hands of God*, and McGilchrist draws his connections in both *The Master and His Emissary* as well as in *The Matter with Things*. I defer a lengthier discussion of these works to another time, suffice it to say that Enheduana's portrayal of Inana should be added to their lists.

As a poet, priestess, author, orator (the context of her *Exaltation* is a kind of court, where she pleads to Inana for help in regaining her position as High Priestess - a notably bureaucratic/political dilemma) and philosopher who perceives the *coincidentia oppositorum* in line with the thinkers mentioned above, as all of these, Enheduana is our Hero here, not necessarily for her morals (as Helle points out, she seems to represent a rather violent acceptance and desire for both power and empire) but for her early status as the first author, one who *writes* beyond the influence of Bureau, who commits her words to depictions of nature and its ways, its contrary forces, over those of made up customs. She sings of death, not of taxes.

Another scholar in this field whom we must mention is the famous Irving Finkel (his being famous but not famous enough is further testament to our made up and mistaken priorities). Finkel speculates (controversially, as he is well aware) that writing did not originate with the Sumerians. Perhaps the technology of writing so much on clay, which in turn has preserved their writing as the oldest, is all there is to it (although perhaps also phonetic writing as opposed to merely pictographic). Either way Finkel finds it difficult to believe that with a building structures such as Gobekli Tepe in modern

Turkey, which is approximately 9000 years old, and where there are stone inscriptions which seem to Finkel like stamps or seals that would have been used on other written materials, therefore we might safely assume that writing on more perishable mediums was prevalent long before the invention of cuneiform clay tablets. Again, however, with the mention of official seals, we also recognize the spirit of Bureau alongside those perished texts. Perhaps we will find some of those texts, somehow, and with them other, earlier Heroes to combat the Villain.

One thing to bear in mind is that here our hero Enheduana was a real person, she existed, she died, and yet - she is remembered. The scholar Gina Konstantopoulos writes about the "three lives" of Enheduana: Her actual life, her life as the author whose writings students had to copy out over and over to learn literacy appropriate to scribes (Bureau's stench permeating throughout the classrooms), and her recent modern revival and recognition today as the first author and even feminist paradigm. The Villain J. Bureau, by contrast, is entirely made up, does not exist, and yet insofar as real *people* continue to follow him, adhere to his rules, aspire to his (ironically human-like) hubris in suggesting that taxes (themselves bureaucratic make-believe) are as inevitable as death, insofar as this continues, so too will this non-existent Villain not go away. J. Bureau is not remembered (how could he be, having just been invented) but instead he and taxes will persist if we insist upon it; his existence is only as certain as that of the *idiom* itself, "death and taxes."

What Follows

SO WHAT follows this look at one of our worst idioms, "death and taxes"? There are, as there ought to be, many questions to ask, queries and investigations to be made, and much research to be done. Among these is a comparative look at ancient terms from various languages and cultures that are somehow equivalent or similar to the modern term 'bureaucracy'. Such studies exist, but a more comprehensive and purposeful inquiry should be made, and the search for the true origins of the spirit of J. Bureau can serve as a kind of guide. How did this noxious fume of a spirit really come about? Does it haunt the halls of all administrative buildings and structures, both modern and ancient? Does it entangle itself with every push of the stylus, scratch of the reed, twirl of the feather and scribble of the pen? Are these technological tools for writing something like wands, reverse-releasing an exhaust 'Bureaurian' fume into our brains?

I have begun the philological and philosophical search into words and concepts of various ancient languages and societies for equivalents to 'bureaucracy', and likewise terms similar to Ancient Geek *technē* and various notions connected with *graphē* ('writing'). Especially interesting are Sumerian terms like the distinction between *Namgalam* ('skilled craftsmanship') and *Me* (a sort of 'divine power' or more-than-human skill which features prominently in Enheduana's *Exaltation*, and is also the category to which writing is assigned instead of *Namgalam*). I would connect these notions to those of the actual buildings, halls and palaces of administrative power called *É-Gal*, and the institute of *Nam-Gub-Sar* or 'scribe-dom' whereby scribes were educated, churned out in factories ('schools') thick with the stench of Bureau's fumes.

Another compelling thread to follow can lead to other mythical figures whose stories may indicate further manifestations of Bureau. For example, the monotonous punishment of Sisyphus pushing his boulder up the mountain only to have it always roll back down again, was, it is sometimes forgotten, in large part due to his having challenged Hades in the Underworld and having sought immortality, to

defeat or overcome death (more than once). Indeed I would venture to suggest that all tales (there are so many) where main characters, such as Gilgamesh himself, seek out to escape death all manifest an odor of Bureau in one form or another.

More must be done, however, if we are to truly identify, isolate, and exorcise this malevolent impostor, this parasitic patron of nothing, this wanna-be deity and failure who seeks to be equal to Nature, even surpass it, but cannot - especially when we stop making mundane offerings and multiple copies of unnecessary stamped, signed, sealed and ever-undelivered 'official' documents, stop standing in lines to the slaughter-houses of numbered windows, the uniformed desks of officialdom and pretenses of power, stop sucking on the noxious toxins of taxation - when we finally stop our false sacrifices to this false god, demon, deity, spirit, pawn-brokering hocker of hubris, this whatever it is we've inadvertently fashioned... a made-up non-entity, a nothing called 'Bureau'; let us be ever vigilant against this Villain, both throughout our daily lives in relation to one another, and what is the same, within the essentially *relational* nature of each other and *ourselves*.

It is on that last note that I would like to finish. For now that the Villainy of Bureau has been established and at least partially portrayed, we can actually see the other side of taxes as such. In many ways taxes represent what Aristotle once told us about money in Book V of the *Nicomachean Ethics*: it is meant as a form of 'justice'. This topic may require its own blog entry, namely a critical look the expression that "money is the root of all evil." For now, let us consider why Aristotle would have said something so seemingly opposite to this and actually identify money with justice. The basic problem is quite simple. How to trade fairly when what is being traded has no common measure? In its most basic form, that is all that money really is, a common measure between incommensurate things. By establishing a common 'currency', a value or quantifiable amount of the same 'stuff' can be assigned to disparate and seemingly incommensurable items or goods, even activities ('labor'). (It is worth noting that Book X of Euclid's *Elements*, which focuses on the 'irrationals', i.e., the *alogoi* and *asummetria* or incommensurable lines, is also where the term *taxis* features most prominently in that work.) Taxes, in their most basic form, are a way to establish the belonging and participation of individuals in a community. As Helle points out in one of the Essays included in his edition of *Gilgamesh*, the usual trade was that of *corvée*, i.e., having to help build via one's labor certain projects designated by the ruler of a city or state. In other words, in exchange for one's labor one gained citizenship. Then, by comparison, we can compare taxes. Helle quotes another scholar: "As the Assyriologist Eva van Dassow points out, the performance of *corvée* became synonymous with 'citizenship', in the same way 'taxpayer' is today" (p. 205). In some sense then, similar to Aristotle's explanation of money as a form of justice that establishes a common measure, so too might we say that taxes allow one to gain citizenship not just by physical labor, but in any number of ways insofar as they can be monetized, i.e., measured and paid via the common measure.

SO WHAT happened to this seemingly flexible, justice-oriented and potentially even more freedom granting method of establishing community, belonging and participation? Was it the Villain that happened? Here I refer the reader back to page one, and invite a rereading of everything that has been said regarding the 'death and taxes' idiom - doing so now, however, with that very question foremost in one's mind: **SO WHAT** 'just' happened?

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